

1 **Frem1 and Frem2 expression in the inner cell mass and TE of the human embryo.**

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6 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
7 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here identification of
8 Frem1 and Frem2 as lineage commitment cooperating factors in embryonic stem cells of the human
9 embryo.

10 Citations

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